

Innovative Methods of Teaching Russian as a Foreign Language

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Abstract: In this article we analyzed innovative methods of teaching Russian as a foreign language. It is very important to study Russian, which is one of the leading languages of the world. All people of the world are not only witnessing to rapid changes in the multifaceted world, but are also direct participants in complex and continuous processes, such as the development and promotion of world culture, science and technology.

Key words: methodology, development, lifelong education, educational technologies, innovative approaches.

The issue of increasing the efficiency of the level of education is perhaps one of the oldest. Over the past few years, many linguists, methodologists and foreign language teachers have been concerned about the problem of finding new and, most importantly, effective teaching methods. Scientists are thoroughly studying existing methods, and at the same time looking for radically new approaches. Disputes in this area do not cease to fade away, what should be the process of teaching foreign languages at school. Some believe that classical methods are the most effective and efficient, while others believe that the techniques that replaced them should replace traditional ones. However, there is a third side of methodologists who believe that the most ideal way would be to combine the classical approach and use new methods.

A significant increase in information and knowledge, an increase in information sources leads to an acceleration of the process of information exchange between teachers and students. It should be noted that there are 3 main properties that characterize modern education today: novelty, dynamism, diversity. It is novelty that dictates the constant updating of the content of classes, as well as methods and forms of teaching.

The requirement for variety in the use of teaching methods in the classroom is also known; for example, methodologists in Western countries believe that a teacher should have 5-8 methods for conducting classes. The more methods and forms of teaching a teacher knows, the more diverse, always in a new way, with a clearer emphasis in setting goals and objectives, he will design his activities.

Let's consider the most popular innovative methods and give a brief description, revealing their content.

The project method is a set of methods and techniques in which students, through individual or collective activities create a project on a specific topic. Taking into account the individual abilities and interests of the student, the task of this method is to create an atmosphere that will motivate the student's activities.

Thanks to the project method, students independently acquire and expand their knowledge, as well as communication skills, working in groups.

The project method will be well applicable in the lessons of regional studies and biography of outstanding scientists and writers.

The game method is one of the most common methods associated with teaching preschoolers and primary schoolchildren. However, this method is also applicable to adult students, and is also quite effective. The game develops the intellectual abilities of students by creating simple situational techniques. For example, for the game “In the hospital”, “At the airport”, “In the store” you need to know and apply vocabulary, grammatical forms and rules. It is in the role-playing game that colloquial clichés, greetings and phrases of “live communication” are widely included.

In practice, I would like to say that students enjoy playing the following games: “LinGo Play”. The language learning app LinGo Play is an interesting and effective vocabulary instructor for learning words and phrases using flashcards and online games, using general questions about the country, hobby, profession, age.

The undeniable advantage of the game method is to increase students' interest in the subject, develop learning motivation and their cognitive activity. All this allows students to learn new things in a natural way and show good learning results. Thus, we can conclude that the game method is one of the most effective methods of teaching Russian as foreign language, since it is as close as possible to real life.

Case-study or the method of specific situations is a method of active situational analysis based on learning by solving specific problem-situations. Students are asked to comprehend professional situations that involve the need to solve a problem.

A case is a description of a real situation or a “photograph of reality.” The situation method contains information that needs to be studied, analyzed, found a solution and proven the correctness of your choice. First, the case is analyzed by each student independently, after which the students are united in pairs or small groups of 3-4 people, where everyone contributes to solving this problem, after which they try to make a common decision. The main feature of this method is that it does not imply a single solution and answer, and the options for the thought process and conclusions on a given problem may differ for all group members.

This case method is quite widely used in the language training of specialists in various fields: psychologists, biologists, economists. However, this method is also applicable for students of foreign languages, but with a sufficient or high level of language proficiency (B1-B2). The case can be used to prepare students for tests, namely the written part, in writing essays. As noted above, the use of this method presupposes the presence of certain basic knowledge of the language. Much attention is paid to working on vocabulary and grammatical structures of the language. The main task is to develop the student's ability to create logically coherent oral and written texts that correspond to a specific topic and situation. This is precisely the main requirement for an essay.

Summing up the results of this method, I would like to note that the case, due to the specifics described above, allows students to use and demonstrate their best sides in class, even in the absence of excellent knowledge of the Russian language.

The theory method for solving inventive problems is a methodology and algorithms for solving creative problems in any field of knowledge that contribute to the development of creative (inventive) thinking and the quality of a creative personality.

The use of theory methods for solving inventive problems in foreign language lessons is becoming increasingly relevant. These methods and techniques make it possible to take into account the student's natural individuality, develop and improve it, and therefore introduce an element of novelty into him. To enhance the creative activity of children, the following theoretical techniques for solving inventive problems are used, such as:

1. Brainstorming is used at various stages of the lesson. It is usually carried out in a group when it is necessary to find a non-standard solution to a problem situation. You can put forward the most incredible solutions that seem crazy. It is necessary that everyone be able to speak out, because, having heard the answers of their classmates, students are happy to put forward more and more solutions in a spirit of competition. For example, when studying the topic “my house”, you can bring pictures of the most unusual houses and ask the children to dream up or ask them to talk about their dream houses.
2. Synectic. This method can be called the method of analogies. Personal analogy (empathy) allows you to imagine yourself as the object or part of the object that is being discussed in the task. Again, using the topic “my house” as an example, you can ask students to imagine themselves in a house on the seashore and describe all the interior items in it.

The theory method for solving inventive problems can be used at any stage of learning. First, individual techniques are mastered, and then they are combined into a system of thinking. Thus, this technology contributes to the education of a creative personality prepared to solve various problems.

IT methods. In recent years, technological progress has accelerated significantly and stepped far forward. Information technologies change not only our lives, but also make significant adjustments to education. More and more we understand that innovative teaching methods are, first of all, digital methods. Training using computer technologies includes:

Authentic language material, such as: videos, podcasts, clips, news. Language learning tools. Applications and programs aimed at learning phonetics, pronunciation, reading, vocabulary and grammar. For example, the Speaking application will “help” students speak Russian, record their remarks, and evaluate how clearly, they speak. With the help of such applications it is convenient to prepare students for speaking, in particular, reading. If students have trouble remembering vocabulary, you can use Quizlet, which will check the necessary words in various types of exercises. If you want to play in a foreign language lesson, you can safely use Wordwall in Russian, where you can find a huge number of games, as well as create your own! Undoubtedly, recently, especially during the relevance of distance education, the interactive virtual whiteboard Miro will also come to the rescue. Electronic dictionaries help students’ complete assignments faster than without technology, and the frequency of dictionary look-ups increases.

The advantage of online audio and video multimedia sources is that students can work with educational material more often. This motivates them and gives them confidence. A large number of studies and practice show that students get more pleasure from using technology when learning a foreign language.

Undoubtedly, modern society is an information society. This is a world of knowledge, ideas and information. Information teaching methods help develop our intellect, enrich cognitive skills, increase creative activity, and make decisions. Innovative teaching methods form an innovative culture of the personality of the future professional.

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